

CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIVEMENT

this cetificate is proudly presented to

NEW INNOVATION IN NATIONAL EDUCATION

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Tursunaliyev E

INFORMATIKA DARSLARIDA

MEDIAMATNLAR TAXLILI

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

OKTABR/ 2022

